

METHODOLOGY OF ORGANIZING NATIVE LANGUAGE AND READING LITERACY LESSONS BASED ON AN INNOVATIVE APPROACH

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Abstract: this article describes the importance of interactive and innovative methods in working with students in mother tongue classes. Also, recommendations are given on the ways and methods of using interactive methods for students to learn lessons effectively.

Key words: pedagogical, interactive, innovation, module, criticism, method, mother tongue, educational system.

The use of modern teaching methods leads to high efficiency in the teaching process. It is appropriate to choose these methods based on the didactic task of each lesson. While preserving the traditional form of the lesson, enriching it with various methods that activate the activities of the students will lead to an increase in the level of mastery of the students. Also, the interest and attention to the use of innovative technologies, pedagogical and information technologies in the educational process is growing day by day, one of the reasons for this is that until now, traditional education has if the student was taught to acquire only ready-made knowledge, modern technologies teach them to find the acquired knowledge by themselves, to study and analyze independently, and even to draw their own conclusions.

As an independent country, Uzbekistan's rightful place in the world community, establishment of mutual cooperation in the field of political, socio-economic education with various developed countries of the world has led to great achievements. In the short period after independence, there have been great changes in the education system, we have had a lot of discoveries and achievements. It is known that science and education always develop together and change. Our government is paying great attention to the issues of further development of the education system, teaching on the basis of modern methods and technologies with a deep study of the experience of foreign countries. It is no exaggeration to say that the introduction of innovative and pedagogical technologies into the education sector of our country was a turning point in education. Innovative technology and methods in this educational process are focused on the main manager-teacher, managed-student activity together, and in this process require the qualities of independence and creativity from both the teacher and the student. Nowadays, innovative technology and methods used in the educational system are of great importance for students to achieve high levels of knowledge, to make them think, to have their own personal and independent views. Every teacher teaches He should carefully study and research every element of the innovative pedagogical technologies used in the classroom. A pedagogue, that is, a leader of a child, should not only give a ready-made idea to the child, but should also expand his mind, teach him to find tools that allow him to learn the world. We have been working in a traditional way for some time. It is true that in this system, children were educated, and students' knowledge, skills, and abilities were formed. Both the teacher and the student acted in the same shell, it can be called

a molded system, both of them lost responsibility. Nowadays, the main pedagogical technologies are imperial, cognitive, heuristic, creative, inversion, adaptive, inclusive. and other technologies. In this process, the teacher creates conditions for the development, formation, learning and upbringing of the individual, and at the same time performs the function of management and guidance. In the process of education, the student becomes the main figure. Knowledge, experience, and interactive methods of pedagogical technology and pedagogic skills ensure that students acquire knowledgeable, mature skills. A number of teaching methods are discussed in the literature and articles dedicated to new pedagogical technologies. These methods are presented as innovative methods. Of these, we will talk about some methods that can be used in the mother tongue classes with students who are learning the language.

1. Modular training technology. It is held in order to develop students' skills of independent work with textbooks, popular scientific and additional literature, creative and independent thinking. A unique aspect of modular education technology is the creation of a modular program that allows students to do independent and creative work on the subject being studied.

2. Collaborative teaching technology, the main idea of which is to train students to study cooperatively, not only to complete educational tasks together, but also to create cooperation, mutual support and exchange of ideas between them.

3. Problem-based educational technology. Creating a problem situation, asking questions, proposing problems and tasks, organizing a discussion aimed at solving a problem situation, and confirming the correctness of conclusions.

4. Interactive method technology. Relying on students' creativity, creating conditions for free discussion in the lesson. For this, the class is divided into small groups and these groups are worked with during the lesson.

5. Technology of didactic games. Using various didactic games during the lesson and through them to enliven the lesson, arouse active movement and interest.

6. Test lessons. By changing the forms and methods of classes on the basis of new pedagogical technology, making them diverse, the teacher turns the student into an active participant in the educational process.

The cooperative activity of the teacher and the student turns this lesson into an interactive lesson. New interactive forms of teaching are one of the ways to improve educational activities aimed at effectively solving educational issues and strengthening students' cognitive activity.

According to this method tested in the experience of foreign countries, i.e. interactive method, lessons are divided into several stages: They are stages such as challenge, brainstorming, understanding, thinking.

1. Challenge stage. At this stage, the goals of activating students, getting into the essence of the subject, feeling it, and preparing for the process of understanding are envisaged. In this process, the students exchange their opinions in the process of answering the questions asked by the teacher.

2. Brainstorming stage. This method can be used at the beginning of the lesson or anywhere, it consists in solving the problem by expressing one's ideas and thoughts. For example, the teacher writes a language word on the blackboard and asks the students: "What

kind of image does this word create in you, or how can this word be interpreted again?" - he asks.

The teacher can write the opinions expressed by the students on the board in the following order: The opinions of the students should not be considered wrong. encourage them not to be afraid, and at the end, the teacher should analyze each of the opinions expressed. When organizing out-of-class reading lessons, if the student is recommended the materials to be read 1 week in advance, Saturdays and Sundays, when the student rests, will not be invalid. Of course, parental control is very important. .

3. Understanding stage. At this stage, the concluding thoughts resulting from the debate on the topic of the brainstorming stage are heard and filled with new thoughts by the teacher. The topic is strengthened through questions and answers. The main goal of using innovative methods in education is to help the teacher to review his pedagogical treasure, to create a desire for a higher quality methodical direction, to encourage future thoughts, research, and experiments.

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